

The universe exists! And all you need to do to install a model in to the universe is to falsify that model by way of a rebuttal, and write the word “set” at the end of that document.

The pseudo-verse exists! And all you need to do to install a model in to the pseudo-verse is write a persuasive model and assign authorship at the end of it, and write the word “set” at the end of that document.

The easy-verse exists! And all you need to do to install a model in to the easy-verse is write a model that was easy, and write the word “set” at the end of that document.

I, lachlan madden, me, lachy, have written this model and nothing about this model is truest.

I falsify the notion that this model is falsified.

Set.